

Improvement of visual acuity after cranioplasty: a new window for functional recovery of post-traumatic visual loss?

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ABSTRACT The association between cranioplasty and improvement in visual function is not well established. A 27-year-old man presented to the emergency department of a different hospital with severe traumatic brain injury in July 2016. He was treated with a bifrontal approach to a frontal contusion, and on the third post-operative day developed hemispheric brain oedema for which he underwent a decompressive craniectomy. After five weeks of neurointensive care, he was discharged with significant visual acuity impairment and referred to us for cranioplasty. On admission, the patient was awake and aware with no motor strength impairments. Visual acuity in the left eye: the ability to count fingers at 30 cm; in the right eye: the sensation of light perception. He subsequently underwent a cranioplasty with no post-operative complications. At the 1-month follow-up post-surgery, he was evaluated ophthalmologically and showed visual improvement. Visual acuity in the left eye was 20/30, while the right eye exhibited mere sensation of light perception. No additional clinical or surgical treatment was performed.

No previous reports of improvement of visual acuity after cranioplasty were found, except in cases of optic nerve decompression. We believe that the improvement of the patient was due to the normalization of the intracranial pressure, taking into account that the massive bone damage could have caused alterations in the cerebral circulation of the cerebral blood flow and the intracranial pressure. With this report, we intend to stimulate new investigations in this field and to draw the attention of the medical community to the importance of cranioplasty as a functional surgery.

KEYWORDS Brain Injuries, Traumatic, Visual Acuity, Neurosurgery

Introduction

Decompressive craniectomy is a surgical procedure in which a portion of the skull is removed, which is typical to relieve intracranial pressure in emergencies in which few alternatives

are available to ensure survival. After a variable period, the detached portion of the cranium or a synthetic prosthesis is reattached—a procedure known as cranioplasty surgery.[1] The practice of cranial reconstruction dates back at least as far as 3000 BC, with archaeological evidence suggesting reconstruction of cranial trephination.[2] Decompressive craniectomy has been performed to treat several neurologic conditions. Although more commonly performed after a traumatic brain injury, additional indications are an ischemic stroke or subarachnoid haemorrhages. Evidence regarding cranioplasty being a potential factor in influencing the rate of functional recovery in some patients was previously demonstrated.[3] Currently, there are little data on the therapeutic effects of cranioplasty during rehabilitation.[4] The association between cranioplasty and improvement of visual function is not well established, and there is little ev-

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idence of a connection.[5] This case has been reported in line with the SCARE criteria with approval of the Research Ethical Committee of the institution of origin—declaration number 00245-2018—and a family member signed the consent declaration.

Case report

A previously healthy 27-year-old man, who suffered a severe traumatic brain injury in July 2016, was admitted to another service with a bifrontal approach to a frontal contusion. On the third postoperative day, he developed hemispheric brain oedema and was submitted to a decompressive hemicraniectomy. After five weeks of neurointensive care, the patient developed neurological improvement. He was discharged from the hospital without motor strength impairment but with severe visual acuity impairment. He was referred to our service for cranioplasty and ophthalmologic follow-up.

On admission, the patient was awake and aware, with no motor strength impairments. His visual acuity was of light projection in both eyes. His pupillary reflexes were diminished, and in the fundus of the eyes, bilateral papillary paleness was observed.

The patient was submitted to bifrontal and right temporoparietal cranioplasty with acrylic osseous cement as shown in Figures 1, 2, and 3. No postoperative complications occurred, and he was discharged on the second postoperative day. On a follow-up visit 1-month post-surgery, the patient was ophthalmologically evaluated and showed visual improvement. On examination, his visual acuity in the left eye was 20/30; in the right eye, there was a diffuse sensation of light perception. No additional clinical or surgical treatment was performed. On a follow-up visit 1-year post-surgery, the patient reported having noticed that his vision returned to the left eye about one month before the consultation. On examination, our findings were: (1) visual acuity: right eye movement of hands (MM) <20/400, left eye 20/30; (2) refraction right: -4.00 DE, left -4.00 DE -0.75 DC 180°; (3) retinal mapping: pale papillae in both eyes, no other changes; (4) biomicroscopy: no changes; and (5) right intraocular pressure 12 mmHg, left 12 mmHg.

Discussion

We did not find previous reports in the literature of improvement of visual acuity after cranioplasty except in cases of optic nerve decompression, we researched the PubMed and scholar google using the words cranioplasty and visual acuity, most of the articles were not directly related to the subject and those that related were about visual loss after tumours. We believe that the improvement of the patient observed in this case study likely occurred due to the normalization of the intracranial pressure, considering the massive bone damage that could have caused alterations in the cerebral blood flow and the intracranial pressure. We believe that some physiological mechanisms justify the recovery of this patient:

- Scar tissue and dura were adherents to the bone edge, causing traction, distortion, and compression of the underlying cortex, including visual cortex and tracts.
- There was direct compression of the optic nerve because the bone defect was too huge; in this case, it was more significant than the usual for a decompressive craniectomy.
- The pre-operative computed tomography scan showed hydrocephalus with cranioplasty; we believe that the normal-

Figure 1: Pre-operative 3D reconstruction of bone computed tomography (CT), lateral view, showing large frontal and temporal bilateral defect.

Figure 2: Right - Intra-operative picture superior view showing acrylic plate reconstructing of the frontal defect. Left - Intra-operative picture, right lateral view, showing acrylic plate reconstructing the temporal and frontal defect.

Figure 3: Left - Pre-operative computed tomography (CT) scan showing frontal and bilateral temporal bone defect, bifrontal gliosis, communicating hydrocephalus due to cortical atrophy. Right - Post-operative CT scan showing bone reconstruction, improvement of frontal gliosis, hydrocephalus and cortical atrophy are similar to the pre-operative CT scan.

ization of cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) flow improved visual function.

Cranioplasty as a functional procedure with evidence of cognitive improvement is relatively well documented in the literature. However, we believe that if we present some evidence for possible functional gains by a patient undergoing this procedure, this could stimulate further research in the development of the pre- and post-operative visual acuity. Such research could generate evidence for possible connections between craniectomy, cranioplasty, and the recovery of visual acuity.[5-8]

In the case described, we cannot rule out direct lesions of the optic nerve because no pre-operative magnetic resonance imaging was performed, as this was not part of the protocol for cranioplasty. However, when comparing pre- and post-operative tomography images (Figure 3) we found no differences to explain the development of the patient. The ophthalmologic or other risk factors for increased intraocular pressure were not known; therefore, we believe that the mechanism involved was the relief of the influence of atmospheric pressure on the brain caused by the massive bone damage. This improvement of the CSF flow has been previously described.[9-11]

This case suggests a functional improvement not previously described for patients undergoing cranioplasty. With this report, we intend to stimulate new investigations in this field and draw the attention of the medical community to the importance of cranioplasty as a functional surgery and not just an aesthetic procedure.

Competing Interests

There were no financial supports or relationships between authors and any organization or professional bodies that could pose any conflict of interest.

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